

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

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**STUDY OF THE FEATURES OF HABILITATION OF A CHILD WITH
DOWN SYNDROME IN THE FAMILY**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
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MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

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